

Beyond One Million Genomes

Recommendations for a 1+MG Data Inclusion Governance Framework

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1. Introduction and Summary

This document recommends standards to ensure genomic and health-related data can be responsibly and effectively made available through 1+MG for secondary use (for research, healthcare and policy-making purposes). These standards focus on ensuring compliance with applicable laws and ethical principles, and promoting transparency of data access and use conditions. Other standards (e.g., data quality) will be addressed by other 1+MG Working Groups.

These recommendations are primarily directed towards 1+MG Data Holders, the institutions with the authority to grant or refuse access to certain genomic and health-related data.¹ A Data Holder is a legal entity (i.e., controller), and must be distinguished from technical infrastructure providers, such as 1+MG certified data hubs where data are physically submitted, pre-processed, stored, and made discoverable and accessible. In the context of the 1+MG federated network, a Data Holder “includes” data by confirming that these standards are respected, meaning that data are legally and ethically ready to be made available. Data inclusion in this context does not mean that data are physically transmitted to a central data pool, or that the Data Holder has given up control over the data.

We recommend the following ethical and legal standards be established for Data Holders:

- Data must be clearly labelled with standard rights metadata describing applicable access and use conditions, to ensure transparency and predictability for data access decisions.
- Data must be subject to a commitment to allow users accessing data through 1+MG to archive their data.
- GDPR transparency requirements must be demonstrably met (and where applicable additional national transparency and/or consent requirements).
- A data protection impact assessment (DPIA) must be conducted to verify and document that making data available in 1+MG complies with both European and national data protection rules and respects the fundamental rights of data subjects.
- For genomes generated in research contexts, a research ethics committee (REC) approval must be obtained for making data available in 1+MG, to ensure ethical obligations around consent, respect for vulnerable groups or individuals, and plans for handling incidental findings are addressed.

¹ Data Holder “means a legal person, public body, international organisation, or a natural person who is not a data subject with respect to the specific data in question, which, in accordance with applicable Union or national law, has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data.” `See a proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance ([Data Governance Act](#)) (Analysis of the final compromise text in view to agreement v 10 Dec 2021) Art 2(5).

- 1+MG intellectual property (IP), commercialization, and publication policies must be accepted.
- A clear recontact policy must be in place describing if and for what purposes recontact is possible (e.g., to access additional/updated data, or to follow-up with a data subject for additional data collection/recruitment).

These requirements are primarily procedural, such as DPIAs and REC approvals, rather than substantive (e.g., specific consent clauses). This ensures flexibility for data coming from different countries and contexts, to be shared subject to different access and use conditions, while also Data Holders demonstrate compliance with legal and ethical requirements. Standards are described as minimum requirements or best practices.

Where the Data Holder is the organisation that originally collected and generated data, such as in the case of a national genomic medicine initiative, it is solely responsible for meeting these standards. Where the Data Holder has received data from another organisation who was the controller for data collection and generation, it is the responsibility of the Data Holder to coordinate with this other organisation to meet the standards.

The role of 1+MG is not to police what data may or may not be ethically and legally included in 1+MG. Rather, the role of 1+MG is to provide support to Data Holders in the form of guidance and checklists to help them prepare for responsible and effective data sharing. National ethics committees and data protection authorities can provide nationally tailored guidelines, and other bodies may be set up to provide advisory services, audit or certification services. While 1+MG cannot take direct responsibility for ethical and legal requirements, it can verify that the Data Holder has appropriately documented compliance.

2. Standards for Inclusion

2.1. Transparency of Data Access and use Conditions

Data Must be Tagged with Standard Rights Metadata Transparently Describing Data Access and Use Conditions (min req): This purpose of this transparency requirement is to allow data requestors to determine if certain genomic and related-health data is actually available to them for their particular purpose. Data access and use conditions will necessarily differ across contexts and countries. This creates uncertainty for data requestors over what data can be accessed, integrated and used. A minimum requirement to ensure predictability for data requestors is that data must be tagged with transparent information on access and use conditions, i.e., with “rights” metadata.

2.2. Fairness for Data Users

Notice Period for Withdrawal of Data from 1+MG (min req): Data Holders must agree to a minimum notice period for withdrawing data, in order to protect the integrity of ongoing analyses, out of fairness to data users already granted access.

Commitment to Archive Data (e.g., completed analyses) (min req): Data Holders must commit to allow data used for research or healthcare purposes to be archived for a certain period of time after the completion of the analysis (e.g., 10 years), to assist data users to meet legal and ethical archiving/reproducibility requirements. The Data Holder must agree to the continued storage of data for archiving purposes even where the archiving period exceeds the retention period for the Data Holder’s purposes.

Limits on Withdrawal of Data (e.g., ongoing analyses) (best practice): Data Holders should agree to refrain from withdrawing access to data once provided for an ongoing analysis.

2.3. Data Protection and Ethics

Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) (min req): Data Holders must conduct a DPIA for sharing the data through 1+MG. A DPIA is a valuable procedural safeguard and accountability tool to ensure documentation that the Data Holder complies with data protection principles. A procedural requirement for data inclusion is also more flexible than having substantive requirements. As data may come with different access and use conditions, they will likely also come with different legal compliance requirements. A DPIA for 1+MG should include the following elements:

- data sharing plan - description of potential data flows through 1+MG.
- lawfulness - legal basis to include data in 1+MG, confirming consent requirements above where applicable.
- transparency - confirming transparency requirements (see below).
- data minimization - confirming data have been appropriately pseudonymised and de-identified before inclusion to 1+MG. 1+MG certified data hubs may assist by further de-identifying data and re-pseudonymising data to apply a 1+MG pseudonym (the resulting data would be “double” coded).
- respect for fundamental rights - processes and contact points must be in place to ensure organisations in the processing chain coordinate so that data subjects can exercise their rights.

Transparency (min req): Data subjects must be provided with detailed information about cross-border access and secondary use for research, healthcare and/or policy making purposes before data are made available through 1+MG. To support this, the 1+MG ELSI WG will prepare a European checklist of core information elements, which can be tailored to include additional national requirements by advisory bodies in Member States. Data Holders will need to document fulfilment of transparency requirements in the DPIA.

Other National Legal Requirements (national min req): There may be additional national legal requirements applicable to the collection context, e.g., requirements for consent content or form, legal instruments to lift medical secrecy around healthcare data. These may be found in biomedical research laws, healthcare laws, biobanking laws etc.

Research ethics committee review and approval (min req): For data coming from research contexts, a REC must review and approve the plan to include data in 1+MG. This is another valuable procedural safeguard that can ensure the following issues are considered and documented:

- respect for ethical consent obligations (or a justified waiver),
- assessment of risks and benefits and safeguards of including special groups,
- an incidental findings (IF) plan is in place that anticipates handling of IFs reported back from 1+MG, and
- data in 1+MG will be subject to appropriate governance and oversight.

Ethics Consent (min req): an ethics consent to secondary use of genomic data (including by external users) must be obtained. This will address the purposes of sharing, the voluntary nature of participation, benefits/risks and their distribution, etc. Some exceptions may be permitted on a national level (e.g., where data sharing from healthcare contexts is based on a law subject to an opt-out consent; where a research ethics committee lawfully waives the consent requirement).

For further guidance see the 1+MG consent, special subjects, and incidental findings policies.

3. Intellectual Property, Commercialization and Publication Policies

Freedom to operate (min req) 1+MG will develop future policies relating to these areas that must be accepted by Data Holders, in order to ensure data users are free to exploit, commercialise, and/or publish their research results, subject to any limitations or conditions agreed upon by Member States.

4. Data Holder/Data Subject Recontact Policy

Several use cases highlight the value of enabling data users to contact Data Holders to request additional information, or to recontact the data subject (e.g., to collect additional information or recruit them into future research projects). At a minimum, it should be clear to data users under what conditions such recontact is possible. Note that recontacting data subjects will normally be more complicated where the Data Holder was not the organisation responsible for the initial collection and generation of data.

Requirement to Tag Data with Transparent *Data Holder* Recontact Conditions (min req): Data Holders must clearly indicate whether or not they are willing to be recontacted by 1+MG data users to provide additional, updated information about data subjects, where the genomic and related-health datasets prove to be insufficient. As a best practice, Data Holders should be willing to respond to such requests from data users.

Requirement to Tag Data with Transparent *Data Subject* Recontact Conditions (min req): Data Holders must transparently indicate to data users which individuals agree to be contacted in the future or not, what organisation is authorised to initiate such contact, and for what purposes (e.g., additional data collection, recruitment). These conditions should ideally expressed using a

standard 1+MG vocabulary. As a best practice, consent from data subjects to be recontacted in the future should be requested, at least for certain purposes (e.g., additional data collection or recruitment), and a mechanism should be in place to initiate recontact on behalf of data users (e.g., maintaining contact details and consent permissions, and establishing a process for re-identification). 1+MG or 1+MG Member Countries could provide assistance by keeping up to date contact lists, and by offering translation where needed.

Beyond One Million Genomes

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Appendix. Background Examples

US National Institutes of Health, dbGaP

- An Institutional Certification must accompany the submission of all large-scale human data to the NIH Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP). Institutions are responsible for assuring, through an Institutional Certification, that plans for the submission of large-scale human genomic data to the NIH meet the expectations of the [Genomic Data Sharing Policy](#)
- The Genomic Data Sharing Policy:
 - requires “Investigators should submit large-scale human genomic data as well as relevant associated data (e.g., phenotype and exposure data) to an NIH-designated data repository in a timely manner.”
 - Investigators should de-identify data according to health research regulation and healthcare privacy law standards, as well as key-code data.
 - “The informed consent under which the data or samples were collected is the basis for the submitting institution to determine the appropriateness of data submission to NIH-designated data repositories, and whether the data should be available through unrestricted or controlled-access.”
 - There is some flexibility for cell lines/clinical specimens collected before the 2015 policy came into force (and after).
- The institutional certification is basically a “data submission agreement” with the institution.² This certifies that the submission:
 - complies with applicable laws and human subjects research regulations.
 - will not disclose research participant identities
 - an ethical consent limitations have been tagged using NIH tags.
 - An Institutional Review Board (IRB) or equivalent has considered:
 - submission and subsequent broad data sharing “is consistent with” informed consent
 - risks to individuals and families of submission were considered
 - risks to groups or populations were considered where relevant/possible.
 - an appropriate de-identification plan is in place.
- Genomic data summary results³ are made publicly available unless the submitter selects controlled-access before of groups risks.

In terms of data quality/standards, dbGaP has Submission Guidelines for 1) Phenotypic and Metadata; and 2) Molecular data⁴, as part of the dbGaP Submission Process.⁵

² https://osp.od.nih.gov/wp-content/uploads/GDS_Extramural_Certification.pdf

³ results from primary analyses of genomic research that convey information relevant to genomic associations with traits or diseases across datasets rather than data specific to any one individual research participant (e.g., genotype counts).

⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap/docs/submissionguide/#1-what-files-do-i-need-to-submit>

⁵ https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/projects/gap/cgi-bin/GetPdf.cgi?document_name=HowToSubmit.pdf

